

1 **AR and GREB1 participate in germ layer lineage choice of pluripotent stem cells.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 The organ systems of the human body are each derived from three germ layers: the endoderm,
7 mesoderm, and ectoderm. We defined here using transcriptomics a minimal set of components required or
8 important for germ layer fate choice to the endoderm in the first trimester of human development. We
9 describe a requirement for AR loss coupled with GREB1 activation in germ layer lineage choice from
10 pluripotent stem cells in *Homo sapiens*.

11 Citations

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